

Maximization of Entropy and Function- Inverse Function Pairs

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 9, 2020

In statistical mechanics, one often calculates the energy distribution $f(e)$ by maximizing the entropy subject to constraints. These constraints are often that the average energy have a particular value and $f(e)$ be normalized. For example, maximizing $-k f(e) \ln(f(e)) + b_1 f(e) + b_2 e f(e)$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Recently in the literature (1), it has been suggested that one may apply this maximization process to the Kaniadakis entropy and obtain the Kaniadakis distribution. The objective of this note is to show that the maximization of entropy subject to an energy and normalization constraint has a formal solution involving a function and its inverse function. For example $\ln(f(e))$ and $f(e)=\exp(-e/T)$ are inverse pairs as are the Kaniadakis log and Kaniadakis exp functions. In particular, one may replace the “ln” function in the entropy expression with the square root function and find the distribution $f(e)=e^2$.

Maximization of Entropy Subject To Constraints

In general, in statistical mechanics one often maximizes entropy subject to constraints such as a normalized $f(e)$ and the expectation value of e in order to obtain $f(e)$. For instance:

Maximize $-k f(e) \ln(f(e)) + b_1 f(e) + b_2 e f(e)$ where b_1 and b_2 are Lagrange multipliers.

This leads to:

$$-k \ln(f(e)) -k + b_1 + e b_2 = 0 \text{ or } f(e) = C_1 \exp(-eb_2) \quad ((1))$$

In (1), it is suggested that one may write a Kaniadakis entropy expression by replacing the natural logarithm “ln” with the Kaniadakis log i.e.

$$\text{Kaniadakis log} = 1/2k [f^k(e) - f^{-k}(e)] \quad ((2))$$

Maximizing entropy subject to normalization and an expectation value for e leads “after some algebra” (1) to the Kaniadakis distribution i.e.

$$f(e) = [\sqrt{1+k^2x^2} + kx] \quad ((3))$$

We wish to argue that the entropy maximization process using an expectation value of energy and normalization allows for a solution of function-inverse function pairs, where the function is the “ln” or its substitute.

Maximization of Entropy with an Energy Expectation Value Constraint

From the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution solution $f(e)=\exp(-e/T)$ one sees that for $T=1$ $\ln(f(e))$ is essentially $-e$ and $-\int de f(e) \ln(f(e))$ the expectation value of energy. In particular, in the maximization equation, one has the two constraint terms:

$$b_1 \int de f(e) + b_2 \int de e f(e) \text{ leading to } b_1 e + b_2 e^2 \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one essentially has $\int de e f(e)$ before maximization. If the object to be maximized is of the same form i.e. also the expectation value of energy, one essentially has a solution to the maximization problem. Thus, if the natural log appears as $f(e) \ln(f(e))$, then using $f(e)$ as the inverse of the natural log immediately converts the “object” into the same form as the constraint and so one automatically has a solution. No matter how one changes the “object”, the constraint changes in the same way because the two are the same.

Thus, if one replaces the natural log in $f(e) \ln(f(e))$ with the Kaniadakis log, then the inverse of the Kaniadakis log is automatically a solution of the maximization problem (if the constraints of normalization of $f(e)$ and the expectation value of e are used). No algebra needs to be performed.

As another example, consider replacing the natural log with the square root function. Then, one maximizes:

$$-k \int de f(e) \sqrt{f(e)} + b_1 \int de f(e) + b_2 \int de e f(e) \quad ((5)) \text{ or}$$

$$-k \sqrt{f} - 0.5 f(e) (1/\sqrt{f}) + b_1 + b_2 e = 0$$

If one assumes that $f(e)$ is normalized, one does not need b_1 . This then leads to $f(e)$ being proportional to e^2 i.e. the inverse function.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one maximizes entropy subject to the constraints of normalization of $f(e)$ and the average value of e , then an automatic solution is to have $f(e)$ as the inverse of the natural log function, or whatever generalized function (say the Kaniadakis log) one uses.

References

Macedo-Fiho, A. Moreira, D.A., Silva R., da Silva ,Luciano. Maximum Entropy Principle for Kaniadakis Entropy and Networks. Phys. Letters A. May 2013.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0375960113000984>